

AUDIT QUALITY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN PUBLICLY QUOTED CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of audit quality on financial performance of consumers' manufacturing organizations in Nigeria. *Ex-post facto* research design was used. Financial performance which is dependent variable is proxied with return on asset (ROA) while audit quality which is the independent variable is proxied with auditors' experience, audit fee and auditors' independence. The population of the study is listed consumer goods firms on Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) and a sample of 10 firms were selected for a period of 10 years (2013 - 2022). This study made use of E-view package version 10.0 to analyze the data. Secondary data were taken from the yearly financial reports of 10 consumer products businesses that are listed on the "Nigerian Exchange Group" (NGX). Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significance level. The results show that auditors' experience (AE), audit fees (AF), and auditors' independence (AI) have positive relationship with return on asset (ROA) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. In addition, there is evidence that AE, AF and AI have insignificant relationship with ROA in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria (AE= 0.305, t-test= 0.348, $p > 0.05$, AF= 0.022, t-test= 0.354, $p > 0.05$ and AI =0.079, t-test= 1.269, $p > 0.05$). This implies that auditors' experience, audit fee and auditors' independence are insignificant factors influencing changes in the financial performance of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. Also, this study reveals an insignificant but positive correlation between audit quality and financial performance. The study concluded that audit quality does not have a significant effect on financial performance. It was recommended that the management of companies should appoint external auditors with relevant industry experience at a reasonable fee, and they should also create enabling environment for external auditors' independence as it affects financial performance.

Keywords: Audit quality, independence, Experience, financial performance, return on asset

1.0 Background the study

Financial reports can have considerable effects on the financial success of quoted companies. Auditing is an essential step in ensuring the financial report is reliable and was prepared in adherence to management policies and accounting standards. It entails examining a company's financial records by independent experts to verify if they conform with accounting standards and laws. Investors rely on financial statements to make reasonable decisions when taking investment decision. Therefore, financial statements must be dependable, reliable, and transparent. There are two types of investors: those who prioritize short-term profits and returns and those who focus on stable long-term gains. According to Bouaziz (2012), auditing plays a crucial role in preventing

conflicts between management and stakeholders concerning potential benefits. The audit report serves as a means of communication between the auditor and other stakeholders. Consequently, it must be clear, objective, and free from any misleading elements to assist users in making informed financial decisions. Audit quality is the ability to provide audit reports with quality and objectivity while assisting users in making decisions based on such findings. In academic literature, It is common practice to use the size of the audit firm, whether it falls under one of the major four or not, as a gauge of the standard of the audit. This study examined how auditing procedures affected Nigerian publicly listed firms' financial results. This study emphasizes importance auditing in improving the financial performance of publicly listed corporations. Concerns about the quality of audits have recently surfaced, especially in the wake of egregious failures like the Enron scandal in 2001, the Parmalat crisis in 2003, and a number of other incidents involving companies like the Cadbury Company Nigeria Plc, AFRI bank Nigeria Plc, the Intercontinental Bank Plc, and Skye Bank Plc. Additionally, a number of company crises that resulted from poor financial reporting have prompted stakeholders in several nations to urge for improved corporate governance (Amahalu, Egolun, & Obi, 2019).

A critical factor in attracting and lowering a company's capital costs is the financial success of firms listed on stock exchanges. An organization with strong financial performance will be appreciated by the investors. Santos and Brito (2012) suggest that the integrity of these financial reports can have considerable effects on the financial success of quoted companies. This study measures financial success in terms of profitability and growth rate. Net profit is the most commonly used metric to define profitability (Bédard & Gendron, 2010). Several indicators, such as the Price Earnings (PE) ratio, Return on Equity (ROE), including Return on Assets (ROA), can be used to evaluate profitability. According to Hamdan, *et. al.*, (2013), all businesses must quantify their benefits as the difference between revenue and expenses. The expansion of a company's size in terms of assets, working capital, and market share, to mention a few, is expressed by its growth rate. This study evaluates financial performance based on the company's profitability, using the revenue ratio before taxes to shareholder equity, which is the standard metric for profitability, according to Chen and Chen (2011). Various metrics, including Price Earnings Ratio (PER), Return on Equity (ROE), and Return on Assets (ROA), are available for evaluating profitability. Nonetheless, in this study, ROA was utilized as the main indicator of financial performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Financial performance

Net profit is the most commonly used metric to define profitability (Bédard & Gendron, 2010). Several indicators, such as the Price Earnings (PE) ratio, Return on Equity (ROE), including Return on Assets (ROA), can be used to evaluate profitability. According to Hamdan, *et. al.*, (2013). financial performance is evaluated based on the company's profitability, using the revenue ratio before taxes to shareholder equity, which is the standard metric for profitability, according to Chen and Chen (2011). Various metrics, including Price Earnings Ratio (PER), Return on Equity (ROE), and Return on Assets (ROA), are available for evaluating profitability. Nonetheless, in this study, ROA was utilized as the main indicator of financial performance.

Audit Quality

Despite the fact that audit quality is well-known in the accounting field, there is no universally accepted definition. Audit quality has been defined differently in various empirical studies. For instance, DeAngelo (1981) characterizes the audit's quality as how the market perceives an auditor's ability to spot and expose significant errors. According to Davidson and Neu (1993), the capacity of the external auditor to recognize and disclose material misstatements and distortions of net income and expenses is referred to as audit quality. According to Arens, *et al.*, (2011), the situation where an auditor discovers and discloses material misstatements within the financial records is a reflection of audit quality. Al-Mousawi and Al-Thuneibat (2011) define audit quality as the extent to which the auditor offers a reasonable opinion. Auditors must apply auditing standards to identify and disclose material misstatements using their methods and judgment. Bedard, Johnstone, & Smith (2010) suggest that an effective audit is one that adheres to GAAS. For the purpose of this study the indicators for measuring audit quality are auditors' experience, audit fee and auditors' independence.

Auditors' Experience.

According to Li, *et al.*, (2018) auditors experience is the number of years an audit firm has been in existence, the kind of clients the firm has, and the quality of training of staff with their professional qualifications. All these factors determine their competence and are positively associated with audit quality. Similarly, Chen, *et al.*, (2019) discovered that auditor experience and industry expertise affected audit quality in the UK. Hidayah and Ariff (2020) also deduced that there is a strong association between auditing expertise and the quality of audits in Malaysia. Furthermore, Ntim, *et al.*, (2019) posited that there is a connection between auditor tenure and the quality of audits in developing African countries.

Audit Fee

The term "audit fee" describes the payment made to an auditor or auditing company in exchange for the services provided in carrying out an audit. Li, *et al.*, (2018) discovered that higher audit fee is connected to improved audit quality in Malaysia. Chen *et al.*, (2019) also found a link between greater audit fees and higher audit quality. In the same vein, Krishnan, *et al.*, (2018) also concluded that, greater auditing costs were positively connected to audit quality in their study of the US firms.

Auditors' independence

Auditors' independence is the ability of the auditor to act with objectivity, integrity and professional skepticism. Auditor should be free from personal or financial relationship that affect his judgement (Olayinka, 2022). Auditor has no business or professional link with a company apart from being appointed the external auditor. Adeyemi and Fagbemi (2018) concluded that there is a connection between audit tenure and independence in Nigeria. According to the study, lower levels of audit independence were linked to longer audit tenures. In addition, Ismail, *et al.*, (2019) found that the UK's auditor appointment procedure for hiring auditors through a competitive bidding procedure improved audit independence. Studies frequently utilize numerous variables, such as auditor tenure, non-audit services rendered, and auditor recruitment procedures, to assess audit independence.

Audit quality and financial performance

The term "Audit quality" encompasses the procedures utilized by auditors to ensure that client organizations adhere to precise quality control standards, allowing them to consistently meet their reporting obligations. According to Bacha, *et. al.*, (2020), audit integrity is defined as the possibility that auditors would find errors in the client's accounting system, and report them. Al-Ahdal & Hashim (2021) found that audit fees, board affiliations, and auditors' independence had a significant impact on the return on assets of corporations and independent auditors were found to have a strong impact on firms' performance. Additionally, Afza and Nasir (2014) concluded that an independent audit's quality positively impacts a company's financial success, thereby enhancing its operational performance from the perception of investors. Bouaziz (2012) contends that high-quality audits can also lead to reduced agent costs, given that auditors offer a dependable and thorough evaluation of financial statements. As a consequence, this could lead to decreased monitoring expenses and enhanced efficiency in a company's operational procedures. A direct connection among the quality of audits and business success was demonstrated by Farouk and Hassan (2014) and Fadzil *et. al.*, (2015).

Theoretical review

Agency Theory

This is the theoretical foundation for this study and it centers on principal-agent relationship that exists between shareholders, who serve as the principal and management who are the agent in publicly quoted firms. As stated by Sarens and Abdolmohhamadi (2007), the agency theory posits that principals and agents act in a rational manner to maximize their wealth, potentially leading to the emergence of the moral hazard problem. Moral hazard, as defined by Jensen and Meckling (1976), refers to a scenario where agents might operate against their principals' best interests in order to increase their pay. Agents are given managerial responsibilities by shareholders and are anticipated to act in the shareholders' best interests. However, agency costs can be reduced by having sufficient audit quality, which arises from information asymmetry and competing interests of shareholders and management. Adequate audit quality can improve financial performance by minimizing information asymmetry, boosting openness and accountability, and enhancing corporate governance. Barry Mitnick and Stephen Ross introduced this hypothesis in 1973. In modern companies, agency theorists support separating ownership from control to avoid conflicts of interest between managers and stakeholders. However, Michael C. Jensen and William Meckling's work on the idea has received the most citations. Information asymmetry makes it difficult for the principals to track how well the agents advance their interests. Defond (1992) is of the opinion that separation of ownership and control is crucial and that the more dispersed an organization's ownership is, the more the owners' and managers' views vary and the more the principals have to watch over and oversee the conduct of their agents. As indicated by Louise (2005), audits assume a crucial role in instilling confidence and strengthening trust in financial information. With the expectation that the agents will operate in their best interests, principals select them and give them decision-making power. Still, principals may need more confidence in their agents due to information asymmetry and differing motives. In such cases, they may resort to measures such as audits to enhance their confidence. Agency theory is relevant to this study because it reduces information asymmetry between the principal (shareholders) and the agent (managers) when a quality audit is conducted.

Empirical Review

Rajasheka, (2022) examined the impact of audit quality and committee characteristics on financial performance. The study used the ROA, ROE, and market capitalization to determine firms' performance in India and the finding was that audit committee has significant effect on ROE and ROA. Also, Muhammad, Rakesh, Moona, and Shamrez (2021) investigated the effect of audit quality on corporate performance of Pakistani firms and the results showed that audit quality has a positive and significant relationship with a firm's success. However, Amanda, Roshan, and Samantha (2019) examined the influence of audit quality on earnings management in Sri Lankan Listed Companies. The results showed an insignificant correlation between audit quality and the level of earnings management.

Also, Yusuf (2020) conducted a study on the impact of audit quality on companies' earnings management in listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria and it was concluded include that audit fee has a negative effect on the management of earnings of listed CGCs in Nigeria. However, audit tenure has positive impact on earnings management. Furthermore, May and Rasha (2019) investigated the effect of Audit Quality on firm performance and the results show that the independence of auditor in BIG4 have an insignificant influence on the dependent variables (ROA & ROE), indicating that the impact of the auditor's expertise and independence on the firm's profitability is minimal. Suzan & Ajay (2021) considered the influence of internal audit quality on financial stability, The results showed that auditors' skill and competence have a significant effect and that there is a positive correlation between the quality of internal audits and financial stability. Iliemena, Okolocha, and Chizoba (2019) conducted a study on the effect of audit quality on financial performance and the results showed that the audit fee and the change in audit firms significantly impact the ROA. Ugwu, Chukwuma, Aikpitanyi, Lilian, and Idem (2020) investigated the effect of audit quality on financial performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria and the findings indicated that audit quality has a positive correlation and insignificant impact on the firm's financial success. Also, the findings indicated that the size of the audit company, the audit charge, and the joint audit had negligible adverse effect on return on assets (ROA). In the same vein, Thu, Lam, Thi, Dung, and Dang (2019) studied the impact of audit quality on financial performance of firms listed on the Hanoi Stock Exchange and the findings show that audit quality positively impacted the financial performance.

Abdullahi, Norfadzilah, and Lateef (2020) examined a study on the effect of audit quality on the financial performance of listed companies in Nigeria. The findings showed there is a positive and significant relationship between auditor independence and size on return on assets (ROA). Ganyam (2020) investigated the effect of the audit quality on profits management of listed Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria. The results show that listed consumer goods businesses' ability to manage their earnings is constrained by audit fees, auditor industry specialty, client significance, and audit opinion. Yilka and Etem (2022) conducted a study on the effect of auditing on insurance company performance in Kosovo. The study conclusions include that the firm's size, leverage, and growth are the most crucial and relevant characteristics. Only the audit mandate has proven to be positively and significantly correlated with the performance of audit firms in Kosovo among audit factors.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Methodology

The expo-facto research design was used. Audit quality is measured by auditors’ experience, audit fee, and the auditor's independence are compared to the dependent variable; financial performance measured with return on assets. Furthermore, secondary data was used for this study because the measurement for the variables are available in the annual reports of the sampled firms. The population of the study is 155 quoted financial and non-financial firms on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at May, 8th 2023. The population according to NGX comprises of the following sectors: agronomy (5), multinationals (6), realtors (8), products (21), financial services (49), healthcare (7), information and communication technology (9), manufacturing goods (13), natural resources (4), oil and gas (10) services (23). The period for the study is ten (10) years ranging from 2013- 2022. Purposive (judgmental) sampling was used as the appropriate sampling method in the study to determine sample size. This study relied on a sample of 10 companies from 4 different sectors: conglomerates, consumer goods, health care and industrial goods for a period of 10 years; 2013-2022. The reason for the choice of the sample from consumer goods firm is because of their importance to the public. Factors considered in determining the sample size of 10 firms are: the companies whose shares had been traded for at least ten years; 2013-2022, and companies that published annual financial reports for year 2013 through 2022.

Table 1 Variable Measurements

Type of Variables	Variables	Measurement
Dependent	Financial performance (ROA)	Net profit/Total asset
Independent variable	Audit quality	
Sub-Independent variables	Audit Experience	Dummy variables are used. For the Big Four audit companies, the value is one (1); otherwise, the value is zero (0).
	Audit Fee	Natural logarithm of audit fees of company (i) over the period of years (t)
	Audit independence	Dummy variables are used. If the company rotates with the auditor, the value will be 1 (one), alternatively it will be 0 (zero).

Descriptive Statistics

This will allow us to see the data obtained during the study process. It allows us to acquire a more exact understanding of the variable distribution.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics

	ROA	AE	AF	AI
Mean	0.089981	0.920000	7.442565	0.800000
Median	0.052995	1.000000	7.409133	1.000000
Maximum	1.000000	1.000000	8.530955	1.000000
Minimum	-0.128919	0.000000	6.903090	0.000000
Std. Dev.	0.149521	0.272660	0.258552	0.402015
Observations	100	100	100	100

SOURCE: Researchers computation 2023

Return on Assets (ROA): From Table 2, the mean value for return on assets is 0.089 and standard deviation is 0.149. The mean value of 8.9% is low and positive, which means that averagely the sampled firms have been experiencing positive return on assets. The standard deviation of 14.9% connotes that there is a dispersion of the return on assets from the mean to the tune of 6.0%, which is a low variation. Thus, the values of the return on assets are close to the mean. The minimum value of -0.128 and maximum value of 1.000 indicate that firms in Nigeria experience different levels of ROA.

Audit Experience (AE): The mean value is 0.92, and the standard deviation is 0.273. This indicates that on the average the sampled firms have 9.7% mean, which means external auditors have low audit experience. The standard deviation of 27.3% shows that the level of variation in ROA from the mean is 17.6% which is also low. The minimum value of 0 (zero) and the maximum value of 1.000 shows that some companies have low return on assets while the ROA is high in other companies.

Audit Fee (AF): According to the descriptive statistics in Table 2 above, the mean value is 7.442, and the standard deviation is 0.258. This indicates that on the average the sampled firms have 744.2% mean, which means external auditors charged high audit fee. The standard deviation of 25.8% shows that the level of variation in AF from the mean is 718.4% which is also high. The minimum value of 6.903 and the maximum value of 8.531 shows that external auditors charge different range audit fee.

Auditors Independence (AI): The statistical value of Audit Independence (AI), the mean value is 0.800, and the standard deviation is 0.402. This indicates that on the average the sampled firms have 80% mean, which means that external auditors have high level of independence. The standard deviation of 40.2% shows that the level of variation in AI from the mean is about 40% which is also high. The minimum value of 0.000 and the maximum value of 1.000 shows that external auditors have different level independence in the discharge of their duties in firms.

Correlation Analysis

This mostly aids in testing the links between the study's independent and dependent variables. An absolute r value shows a significant connection between the factors, whereas the negative symbol in front of the r value implies a negative correlation, depending on the course of the association. The Pearson coefficient, which has a value between -1.00 and +1.00, may be used to assess the significance of the relationship between two variables. Cohen (1988) suggests that the outcome, which has a possible range of 0 to 1, has a significance. A correlation of 1.0 indicates a faultless positive connection, -1.0 indicates a flawless negative correlation, and 0 indicates there is absolutely no link. The correlation matrix was used to try to look at the relationship among the independent and dependent variables. The correlation matrix shows how every dependent and independent variable in the research relates to one another. The tables below present the findings;

Table 3 Correlation Matrix

Covariance Analysis: Ordinary Date: 06/26/23 Time: 15:58 Sample: 2013 2022 Included observations: 100					
Correlation t-Statistic Probability	ROA	AE	AF	AI	FA
ROA	1.000000 ---- ----				
AE	0.121989 1.216718 0.2266	1.000000 ---- ----			
AF	0.139303 1.392606 0.1669	-0.106482 -1.060143 0.2917	1.000000 ---- ----		
AI	0.206516 2.089444 0.0393	0.589768 7.229569 0.0000	-0.086767 -0.862200 0.3907	1.000000 ---- ----	
FA	-0.004780 -0.047320 0.9624	0.543693 6.412944 0.0000	-0.030689 -0.303947 0.7618	0.263393 2.702902 0.0081	1.000000 ---- ----

SOURCE: Researchers computation 2023

As stated in Table 3 above, Return on Assets (ROA) has a weak and positive correlation with Audit Experience (AE), Audit Fee (AF) and Audit Independence (AI) with a value 0.121, 0.139 and 0.206 respectively. According to the positive association between AE, AF and AI, the positive correlation implies AE, AF and AI will lead the increase in financial performance, as measured by ROA. It also implies that companies with more audit experience may have better financial performance compared to those with less audit experience. It suggests that the expertise, knowledge, and skills gained through previous audit engagements contribute positively to a company's ability to generate higher returns on its assets and positive correlation with Audit Fee implies that as the audit fee increases, financial performance, as measured by ROA, will also increase. It implies that companies that pay higher audit fees may experience better financial performance compared to those that pay lower audit fees. It suggests that investing in quality audits, which often come with higher fees, may lead to improved financial performance and higher returns on assets. More indications regarding the positive correlation with Audit Independence implies as the level of audit independence increases, financial performance, as measured by ROA, will also increase. It implies that companies with a higher degree of auditors' independence will impact financial performance compared to those with lower levels of auditors' independence.

Table 4: Regression results

Variables	Coefficient	t-test	Probability
Contant	-0.1175	-0.2490.	0.8037
Auditors' Experience	0.0305	0.3476	0.7290
Audit Fees	0.0221	0.3540	0.7242
Auditor's Independence	0.0791	1.2698	0.2073
Firm's Age	-0.0014	-8.8468	0.3992

R-Square 0.0278

SOURCE: Researchers Computation 2023

Table 4 shows the results of regression analysis of the effects of audit quality on financial performance of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The results show that auditors experience (AE), audit fees (AF), and auditors' independence (AI) have positive relationship with return on asset (ROA) of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. In addition, there is evidence that AE, AF and AI have insignificant relationship with ROA in quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria (AE= 0.305, t-test= 0.348, $p > 0.05$, AF= 0.022, t-test= 0.354, $p > 0.05$ and AI =0.079, t-test= 1.269, $p > 0.05$). This implies that auditors' experience, audit fee and auditors' independence are insignificant factors influencing changes in the financial performance of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

The Adjusted R^2 which measure the proportion of changes in the financial performance of quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria as a result of changes in auditors' experience, audit fee, and auditors' independence explains about 3% changes in the financial performance, while the remaining 97% were other factors explaining changes in the financial performance of quoted consumer companies in Nigeria but were not captured in the model.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses of this study effort were tested and addressed in this part. The result of the random effect regression was used to conduct the test using t-statistics and their associated p-values The study accepts alternative at a 5% level of significance or less. The tested hypothesis's findings are as follows:

Hypothesis 1 - Audit fee has a significant effect on financial performance in publicly quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. With a p-value of 0.7242, the panel's least square analysis result shows that the Audit fee is higher than 5% level of significance. As a result, we do not reject the null hypothesis that audit fees do not significantly affect the financial performance of publicly traded consumer goods businesses in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2 - Audit independence has a significant effect on financial performance in publicly quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. With a p-value of 0.2073, Audit Independence is higher than the 5% level of significance in the set of least square regression result. As a result, we

do not reject the null hypothesis that audit independence does not significantly affect the financial performance of publicly traded consumer products businesses in Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3 - Audit experience has a significant effect on financial performance in publicly quoted consumer goods companies in Nigeria. With a p-value of 0.7290, the panel's least-squares regression result shows that Audit Experience is higher than the 5% level of significance. As a result, we do not reject null hypothesis the that Audit Experience do not significantly affect the financial performance of publicly traded consumer products businesses in Nigeria. This is consistent with the findings of, May & Rasha, (2019).

Discussion of Findings

The study's primary goal was to ascertain how audit quality affected financial performance in publicly quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The study found that audit fees had a positive but insignificant effect on financial performance, i.e., Return on Assets, with a stated a p-value of 0.7242. This implies that if audit fees rise, it will not significantly affect financial performance. The study contradicts the conclusions of related earlier studies by Yusuf (2020), whose empirical result revealed that audit fees had a considerable adverse impact on the management of earnings of listed CGCs in the country. Examining the impact of audit independence on financial performance was the study's second hypothesis. The study found auditor's independence has a positive and insignificant effect on financial performance, with a p-value ($0.2073 > 0.05$). This means that audit independence will not lead to any significant increase in Returns on Assets. Even though, this study does not confirm the significant effect of audit independence on financial performance, audit has no value without independence and opinion of the auditors validates the quality of financial reports. This study contradicts the conclusions of Abdullahi, Norfadzilah, Umar, & Lateef, (2022), who found that the Auditor Independent was positively and significantly correlated with financial success as assessed by return on asset. The third objective of the study was to examine the impact of audit experience on financial performance. The study showed that Audit Experience has a positive but not significant. The study found an association between audit experience and returns on assets, however it was not statistically significant, with a reported t-value of 0.347520 and a p-value of ($0.7290 > 0.05$). This shows that Return on Assets will rise together with the degree of audit experience but the rise is insignificant. This agrees with the findings of (May & Rasha, 2019) that that the auditor experience has a negligible effect on the firm profitability. The outcome of this study is not far from reality because external auditors' activities do not interface with the day-to-day operations of the firm. Also, external audit takes place after the books have been closed for the year.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are put forward:

1. Management should appoint external auditors with relevant experience in their industry since long years of experience does not significantly affect financial performance.
2. Management are advised to appoint external auditors with affordable audit fee to sustain their financial performance.
3. The board should create enabling environment for the external auditors to preserve the independence of the auditor as it has a positive effect on financial performance.

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